

Using acorns in innovative foods for human consumption could contribute to preserving Portuguese agroforestry systems and the environment

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ABSTRACT

Modern food systems require diversification across both production and consumption to achieve better health for planet and people. We study the environmental impact associated with the use of acorns as ingredients for direct human consumption – as opposed to animal feed – from an agroforestry (montado) system in Portugal, using different allocation approaches for land occupation and carbon sequestration. We show that the four acorn-based products assessed - burger patties, pâté, flour and fermented acorns - are associated with carbon savings when above- and below-ground carbon sequestration is accounted for, with (negative) carbon footprints as low as -88.1 kg CO₂ equivalents per kg of flour. Whilst meat-substituting acorn products are associated with significantly lower environmental burdens than their conventional alternatives, fermented acorns and acorn flour, which replace plant-based foods, are associated with significantly higher burdens across other impact categories, notably marine eutrophication 28 to 267 times higher for fermented acorns than olives. Higher burdens across these categories largely reflect high nitrogen input from animal manure deposition, which exceeds the critical load range for N for this type of ecosystem and should be reduced. Production of novel food products from acorns could support maintenance or expansion of montado systems, enhancing diversity and carbon storage in the landscape whilst displacing more environmentally damaging food products.

1. Introduction

Montado systems, also called *dehesa* in Spain, are agro-silvo-pastoral systems typical of the Mediterranean regions of Spain and Portugal, covering >4 million hectares (Guimaraes et al., 2023). They are characterised by oak trees (*Quercus* sp), shrub, and grass layers with cattle, goats and sheep (Joffre et al., 1999). *Quercus suber*, one of the two main oak species, is used for cork production while *Quercus rotundifolia* (holm oak) is traditionally used for feeding Iberian pigs. Acorns, the nuts of the oak tree, are a source of fibre, protein, vitamins A and E, minerals, unsaturated fatty acids, and phenolic compounds (Vinha et al., 2016). Their use as a source of human food in the Iberian Peninsula goes back to Prehistorical times as a resource during food shortages. However, since the 1960s, they represented poverty and food for the ancient generation (García-Gómez et al., 2017). Nowadays, acorns are used as a versatile ingredient for human consumption, such as coffee substitutes, noodles, cooking oil, and flour-derived products. In some regions of the World, such as Korea, large quantities of acorns are used for making dotorimuk, a popular jelly (García-Gómez et al., 2017). Although the use of acorns

as a food source has a wide geographical spread (Bainbridge, 1986; García-Gómez et al., 2017; Overstreet et al., 2015; Torche, 2024), the direct human consumption of acorns in Europe is limited and is therefore considered an under-utilised crop. Recent studies investigating marketability and consumer acceptance of acorn-based foods, show a marked influence of product type (Pasqualone et al., 2019), percentage of acorn incorporation in the recipe and processing method (Molavi et al., 2015), and consumer expectation and awareness of the presence of the ingredient (Noci, 2014). Some products are more suited to acorn ingredients, such as cookies, where acorn biscuits present desirable properties such as friability, colour, and a larger volume (Pasqualone et al., 2019). Regarding acorn as an ingredient in meat substitutes, a recent study developed vegetable spreads as alternatives to traditional meat pâtés and assessed consumer acceptance based on colour, consistency, texture, odour and taste, alongside nutritional value (Socaciu et al., 2023). The authors found an overall reasonable acceptance rate for all products, and a higher purchase intention for the pâté containing 5 % beech achene kernel powder and 5 % sessile oak acorn kernel paste.

Acorns are increasingly gaining attention as a nutritious food source (Pasqualone et al., 2019). Acorns are a rich source of bioactive

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Nomenclature

$AF_{Acorn,Enterprise}$	allocation factor of the acorn enterprise for the whole Freixo do Meio farm
$AF_{Product}$	economic allocation factor of the acorn product type (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) for the acorn enterprise
$C_{seq,AG}$	aboveground carbon sequestration of oak trees in Freixo do Meio (t CO ₂ eq. ha ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹)
$C_{seq,BG}$	belowground carbon sequestration of oak trees in Freixo do Meio (t CO ₂ eq. ha ⁻¹ .year ⁻¹)
$C_{seq,product,Scenario}$	carbon sequestration attributed to 1 kg of acorn product (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) in a specific scenario (Integral, Intermediate, or Focused) (t CO ₂ e per kg acorn product)
Harvested	amount of acorns harvested (t.year ⁻¹)
Holm	percentage of holm oaks in the oaks mix in Freixo do Meio
$Land_{Product,Scenario}$	land occupation for the production of 1 kg acorn product (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) in a specific scenario (Integral, Intermediate, or Focused) (ha)
Product _{Sold}	amount of products sold of a same type (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) (kg)
Surface _{Scenario}	total surface area modelled for acorn harvesting in a specific scenario (Integral, Intermediate, or Focused) (ha)

compounds that assist in preventing numerous diseases such as Alzheimer's and diabetes, and are of interest for individuals with celiac disease due to their gluten-free nature (Dordevic et al., 2025). Acorns are also abundant in dietary fibre and minerals such as iron, calcium, copper, and manganese (Dordevic et al., 2025). Tannins, which are anti-nutritional compounds and require leaching before human consumption, vary in quantities depending on the oak species. While numerous acorn species have a high tannin content, others, such as *Quercus rotundifolia* - the species investigated in this study - are characterised by their particularly low tannin content and therefore do not require any form of pre-consumption treatment, and can even be eaten fresh (Brand, 2019). As acorns are characterised by a rich nutritional profile and are an underutilised food source, Vinha et al. (2016) call for studies that promote new health-promoting and market competitive acorn products. Assessing the environmental impact of such foods is one of the factors that potential customers consider when making purchase decisions (Nicolau et al., 2021).

Montado systems play a key social, economic, and environmental role in the Mediterranean region. In addition to montado systems supplying food and forest products, they provide employment, preserve biodiversity, store carbon, prevent wildfires, protect against erosion and desertification, and preserve local knowledge and traditions (Guimaraes et al., 2023; Parra-López et al., 2023; Pineda and Montalvo, 1995). However, the conservation of montados is challenged, due to low economic profitability, changing climatic conditions (water shortages in summer), and improper management such as over-exploitation of tree cover and overstocking of cattle (Parra-López et al., 2023; Sousa-Correia et al., 2007). Considering the numerous advantages and threats facing the montados, it is necessary to adopt practices that preserve this ecosystem and ensure sufficient economic income. One potentially sustainable revenue stream is the marketing of acorns for direct human consumption.

There are currently no Life Cycle Assessment (LCA) studies for acorns used as a direct product for human consumption. LCAs involving oak trees either assessed the environmental impact of meat or milk

production in montado systems (Eldesouky et al., 2018; Escribano et al., 2022; García-Gudiño et al., 2020; Horrillo et al., 2020; Lammatou et al., 2022; Reyes-Palomo et al., 2022, 2023), or the impact of cork production (Dias et al., 2014; González-García et al., 2013). While none of the studies with an animal product functional unit considered oak tree management practices in the life cycle inventory, those of cork production did. Different approaches to calculate carbon sequestration were adopted in these studies. González-García et al. (2013), Dias et al. (2014), and García-Gudiño et al. (2020) explicitly excluded carbon sequestration from their system boundaries, whereas the remaining studies estimated above-ground, below-ground, or both sequestration types using generic values (Eldesouky et al., 2018; Horrillo et al., 2020) or direct soil measurements (Reyes-Palomo et al., 2023). Although it is not a LCA study but a biophysical assessment, Laporta et al. (2021) focused on carbon stock changes in montado systems using national inventory reports. A summary of the approaches is recorded in Table S1.

Our study is the first to our knowledge to evaluate the environmental impact of using acorns for direct human consumption through various food products, investigating the sensitivity of environmental footprints to different accounting approaches for land occupation and carbon sequestration from trees. Through an attributional cradle to farm gate LCA of multiple acorn products and their conventional counterparts using European Product Environmental Footprint Category Rules Guidance (PEFCR) (European Commission, 2018) the objectives of this study are to:

- Provide the first environmental footprints of novel acorn food products compared with conventional, market alternatives.
- Explore different approaches for allocating land occupation and carbon sequestration to products arising from complex, multi-functional agroforestry systems.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Goal, scope, and system boundaries definition

The goal of this LCA is to evaluate the environmental impact of using acorns from the montado system for direct human consumption through various food products, investigating the sensitivity of environmental footprints to different accounting approaches for land occupation and carbon sequestration from trees. This study is intended for researchers, agricultural practitioners, and stakeholders interested in alternative food systems, agroforestry practices and representation of multifunctional systems in LCA. The study provides the first environmental footprints for four novel acorn-based foods and compares them with conventional market alternatives:

- Acorn burger patty versus a beef burger patty and a soy-based patty. The beef patty was chosen as beef is the most typical meat used for burgers, while the soy patty was selected as it is a common vegetarian alternative with availability in the Agribalyse database.
- Acorn flour versus wheat flour. Wheat flour is the most common flour type in Europe and is used for similar purposes as acorn flour (e.g. bread and biscuits).
- Acorn pâté versus chicken and pork terrine. Both are spreadable products with the same intended use, and data for the terrine was available in the Agribalyse database.
- Fermented acorns versus fermented olives. Both products are aperitif foods and undergo similar final processing steps.

The functional unit was defined as the production of 1 kg of food product. Such a functional unit was selected as it was considered that the products compared (e.g. acorn burger patty versus beef burger patty) were similar enough to have the same serving sizes, and that consequently a mass functional unit was acceptable for comparison purposes. Indeed, consumers at the farm's restaurant would typically have the

choice between a vegetarian acorn burger patty option or a beef burger patty, independently of the different nutritional values of the two products. While a nutritional functional unit would also be interesting to use for the comparisons, not all nutritional information was available for the acorn products.

System boundaries are from cradle to production of the food at farm gate, without packaging (Fig. 1). The study is based on a case study of Freixo do Meio, a montado farm located east of Lisbon, Portugal, in the Alentejo region. Freixo do Meio is a complex, multi-output agro-silvo-pastoral agroecological ecosystem, with oak trees spread in a non-linear way over the whole surface of the farm. The percentage of cork and holm oaks in Freixo do Meio are 30 % and 70 %, respectively over a surface of 480 hectares, with an average tree density of 70 per hectare. One of the farm’s particularities is that it uses holm oak acorns to produce human foods, ranging from breads and biscuits to meat substitutes. Because the exact yield of acorns produced in Freixo do Meio was not known, the mean yield provided by Gea-Izquierdo et al. (2006) was used, amounting to 387 kg of acorns produced per hectare. However, yields can differ greatly depending on the year, location, and neighbouring trees (Crous-Duran et al., 2016). Therefore, a triangle distribution was applied to the acorn yield, with a + and -50 % variation and a mode equal to the literature value indicated above.

At Freixo do Meio, ancestral animal breeds have been selected to mimic as far as possible a “natural” system for the “regeneration” of soils and pastures. The Freixo do Meio system possesses 160 Barrosã cattle, 450 Alentejo pigs, 250 black merino sheep, and 40 Lusitanian chickens, which are carefully managed to condition the land and remove the need for most agricultural machinery interventions on soils. Since 2005, the

Freixo do Meio farm has been developing acorn food products for human consumption, the first sales of which occurred in 2008. Partnering with other companies, Freixo do Meio created a quality association named Confraria Ibérica da Bolota (CIB) (*Confraria Ibérica da Bolota*, 2020). Freixo do Meio developed a diverse portfolio of acorn food products, including acorn infusions (coffee substitutes), burger patties, pâtés, flour, biscuits, cakes, sweet breads, bread and toasts, dried acorns, and fermented acorns. These products are currently sold by Freixo do Meio and have demonstrated a positive consumer acceptance and willingness to buy. Besides the acorn production chains, Freixo do Meio produces and commercialises other food products, including olive oil, pork, beef, lamb, and chicken products, fruits, and vegetables.

Processing happens within the farm. This study tried to overcome the challenge arising from having numerous farm outputs that are inherent to this mixed (montado) system by dividing the Freixo do Meio farm into various “enterprises”, representing the different businesses, such as the acorn enterprise, the cork enterprise, the animal enterprise, the horticultural enterprise, etc. This is in accordance with the ISO guidelines, which recommend dividing the multifunctional process into sub-processes wherever possible so that the functions of the system are clearly identified (International Organization for Standardization, 2006). Oak trees are a key part of all the enterprises of the farm. Besides the most obvious services such as providing cork through their bark for the cork enterprise, they also provide food and shade for the animals through their acorns and canopy. They are part of the tourism enterprise, in that groups come to Freixo do Meio to visit the multi-functional system, enjoy the landscape, and there is a tour specific to acorns.

The LCA in this study was performed for the acorn enterprise,

Fig. 1. System boundaries of the acorn value chains, within the wider montado (agroforestry) system.

allocating oak tree management burdens and carbon storage between the various enterprises through an economic allocation. Emissions associated with (animal-related) nutrient cycling-related emissions are accounted for and partly allocated to the acorn as human food enterprise. This approach is described further below.

2.2. Life cycle impact assessment method

All products were assessed against the sixteen impact categories of the Environmental Footprint Method EF 3.0 in the Ecoinvent 3.9.1

Table 1

Life cycle inventory of the acorn products. Different carbon sequestration approaches used are explained later in the text.

Stage	Input / output / process	Units	Fermented acorns		Acorn burger		Acorn pâté		Acorn flour	
			In	Out	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out
Agricultural stage	Diesel, for tractor	L	0.11		0.03		0.03		0.14	
	Occupation, forest, extensive (Focused/Intermediate/Integral)	m ²	25/12/112		44/20/196		57/26/255		35/16/155	
	AG Carbon sequestration from oaks (Focused/Intermediate/Integral)	kg CO ₂ eq.	3.0/1.4/13.5		5.3/2.4/23.5		6.9/3.2/30.5		4.2/1.9/18.6	
	BG Carbon sequestration from oaks (Focused/Intermediate/Integral)	kg CO ₂ eq.	7.5/3.5/33.3		13.1/6.1/58.3		17.0/7.9/75.6		10.4/4.8/46.0	
	Manure deposition (Focused/Intermediate/Integral)	kg N	0.32/0.15/1.43		0.10/0.05/0.44		0.09/0.04/0.38		0.42/0.19/1.87	
	Selection	Acorns, shelled, for sowing	kg		0.13		0.04		0.03	
Drying phases	Water, evaporated	kg		0.3		0.09		0.08		0.4
	Wood pellets (purchased) that are burnt	kg	0.29		0.09		0.07		0.37	
Breaking and Shelling	Electricity, for breaking and shelling	kWh	0.03		0.01		0.01		0.04	
	Acorns shells for pig feed or put back to soil	kg		0.34		0.1		0.09		0.44
Blowing	Electricity, for blower	kWh	0.001		0.0004		0.0004		0.0018	
	Spoiled acorns and remaining shells - go back to animals or soil	kg		0.17		0.05		0.04		0.2
Acorn flour production	Electricity	kWh						0.0075		
	Acorn flour	kg								1
Fermented acorns production	Orange peels	kg	excluded							
	Laurel leaves	item	excluded							
	Salt	kg	0.09							
	Oregano	kg	excluded							
	Water	L	0.23							
	Fermented acorns	kg		1						
Acorn burger production	Potato	kg			0.43					
	Electricity for acorn crumbs production	kWh			0.01		0.01			
	Chickpea flour (organic)	kg			0.12					
	Electricity for flour production	kWh			0.01					
	Garlic (organic)	kg			0.05					
	Carrot (organic)	kg			0.06					
	Olive oil (organic)	kg			0.04					
	Electricity for olive oil production	kWh								
	Swelite (pea fiber)	kg			0.02					
	Tomato pulp (organic)	kg			0.03					
	Beetroot (organic)	kg			0.03					
	Salt	kg			0.02					
	Parsley (organic)	kg			excluded					
	Oregano (organic)	kg			excluded					
	Electric boiling	kWh			1					
	Tap water for boiling	kg			2					
	Wastewater, average	L					1.1			
Water emission to air	kg					0.12				
Acorn burger	kg					1				
Acorn pâté production	Chickpea flour (organic)	kg					0.13			
	Energy for making chickpea flour	kWh					0.01			
	Potato (organic)	kg					0.11			
	Garlic (organic)	kg					0.01			
	Salt	kg					0.01			
	Olive oil (organic)	kg					0.26			
	Water	kg					0.67			
	Pepper paste	kg					0.07			
	Coriander	kg					excluded			
	Ground black pepper	kg					excluded			
	Oregano	kg					excluded			
	Electric boiling	kWh					0.17			
	Tap water for boiling	kg					2			
	Wastewater, average	L							0.8	
	Water emission to air	kg							0.1	
	Acorn pâté	kg							1	

2.3. Acorn enterprise system

The only agricultural machinery used to manage the oak trees is a roller crimper that breaks the vegetation and leaves it to rest on the floor. It is used once a year over the 480 hectares of the montado. The oak trees, which are over 100 years old, produce acorns four times a year, but acorns are harvested only from the holm oaks at the third crop of each year, between November 24th and January 14th for the years studied here. Diesel consumption for the harvesting stage was calculated using economic records, and deduced as a volume from the average national diesel prices in Portugal in 2021 (European Commission, 2023), i.e. 1.437 euros per litre. Acorns are handpicked simply using a stick to shake trees and a tractor, and with a Bag-A-Nut hand tool. In the 2020–2021 cycle, a total of 4459 kg of acorns with a moisture content of 33.6 % was collected on a 50 ha-surface. This amount represents a small proportion of the actual acorns produced from the holm oaks, as most acorns remain on the ground, and a portion of these are also eaten by the animals.

Harvested acorns are transported by tractor to the farm infrastructure, followed by another selection step by hand. Approximately 340 kg are kept for sowing, and 4119 kg are kept for processing. A selection of 5 kg is then brought to be sold fresh in the local store, and the 4114 kg remaining are left to be partially dried under a protective roof for 15 days, during which birds also come to eat the bugs. This is followed by a second drying step, consisting of placing the acorns in a smokehouse on a wooden platform and using two heaters powered by the burning of 741 kg of wood pellets per day for 15 days. The burning of wood pellets was captured in the LCA using the Ecoinvent process “heat production, wood pellet, at furnace 9kW”, which includes emissions to air, including the biogenic carbon released (Wernet, 2016) based on the weight of the wood. A total of 3313 kg of dry acorns with a 18 % moisture content is obtained. From the start of February 2021, the breaking and shelling process took place, which consists of breaking the acorns into larger pieces, using a specific machine that processes 30 kg of acorn per hour with a 0.7 kW consumption. A blower to separate the shells from the core part of the acorns is then used, consuming 2.2 kW. From this step, 876 kg are obtained for pig feed or ground cover and the remaining 2437 kg are placed for further selection. This selection step consists of separating spoiled acorns and remaining shells, resulting in an additional 439 kg of rotten acorns and shells for pig feed and the remaining 1998 kg selected as clean acorns ready for further processing into infusion powder, fermented acorns, and crumbs and flour that are then used to produce the burgers, pâtés, bread, and other products.

The following part of the text describes the products assessed, and the life cycle inventory is recorded in Table 1. Environmental burdens of acorn products were compared with burdens of their conventional alternatives. Fermented acorns were compared to an adapted process of “Olive, green, stuffed” from the Agribalyse v.3.1.1 database (Colomb et al., 2015), where the stuffing weight was replaced by olive. The same carbon sequestration as the theoretical *Focused* approach was assigned based on land occupied for olive production. Carbon sequestration happening in the *Focused* approach was chosen as it was assumed that the olives were grown as stand-alone crops in olive groves.

2.4. Acorn flour

Once acorns go through the processes described in Section 2.3, the unshelled acorns are passed through a bread grinder with a capacity of 100 kg/hour and an energy consumption of 0.75 kW for an output of 1 kg of flour. All these steps happen on farm.

2.5. Acorn crumbs

Preliminarily processed unshelled acorns (Section 2.3) are passed through a stone grinding mill with a capacity of 40 kg/hour and an energy consumption of 1.1 kW for an output of 1 kg of acorn crumbs.

This happens on farm.

2.6. Fermented acorns

Preliminarily processed unshelled acorns (Section 2.3) go through the same processing as the one for fermenting olives. The acorns are mixed with water, salt, and aromatic ingredients such as orange peels and laurel leaves before being left to ferment for three months. The inventory excluded these aromatic ingredients, as they were not available in the database and represented minor quantities in the recipe (each ingredient represented <1 % of the recipe). This happens on farm.

2.7. Acorn burger

Once acorns are harvested and processed as described in Section 2.3 and transformed into crumbs, they are mixed with chickpea flour, garlic, carrots, olive oil, pea fibre, tomato pulp, beetroot, salt, parsley, and oregano. Most of the ingredients are organic and come from the farm. However, no data were collected for the secondary ingredients. Therefore, secondary data were used from the Ecoinvent v.3.9.1 cut-off database (Wernet, 2016), and conventionally-produced crops were used when no organic option was available (all but potato). Carrot and onion production LCA data were available for representative of systems in the Netherlands, while olive production LCA data were available for Spanish systems (Wernet, 2016). Olive oil production energy values and water consumption were extracted from the Agribalyse v.3.1.1 database (Colomb et al., 2015). Onion production was used as a proxy for garlic. Processing of ingredients was performed with a kitchen robot and a stove. The process of industrial boiling (Colomb et al., 2015) was used as a proxy for energy and water use values. Each burger has a weight of 100 grams. Parsley and oregano were not modelled due to missing data in the database, and because they are added in minor quantities (<1 % of mass balance of all ingredients). Completeness of the inventories for all products was recorded in Table S2 (Supplementary Information). All processing steps happen on farm.

2.8. Acorn pâté

After acorns are harvested and processed as described in Section 2.3 and transformed into crumbs, they are mixed with chickpea flour, cooked potatoes, garlic, salt, olive oil, water, pepper paste, coriander, ground black pepper, and oregano. Most of the ingredients are organic and come from a separate enterprise on the same farm. However, like for the acorn burger, secondary data were used from the Ecoinvent v.3.9.1 cut-off database (Wernet, 2016), and conventionally-produced crops were used when no organic option was available (all but potato). A process for bell pepper “Rest of World” was used as a proxy for pepper paste. Oregano, coriander, and black pepper were not modelled. No energy data for mixing were available and this step was therefore ignored. This happens on farm.

2.9. Land occupation and carbon sequestration

This study integrated both above- and below-ground carbon sequestration, as these are key differentiating parameters defining such agroforestry systems. The above-ground carbon sequestration value of Laporta et al. (2021) was used in this study, as the authors used Portuguese national inventory reports that are based on the IPCC guidelines (De Klein, 2006) and their values are within the range of values found in the literature as described further in the text. The below-ground carbon sequestration value of Reyes-Palomo et al. (2023) was used in this study, as it mentions a similar number of trees per hectare than in Freixo do Meio, whereas other studies integrating below-ground carbon sequestration did not take into account the number of trees (Eldesouky et al., 2018; Escribano et al., 2022; Horrillo et al., 2020).

The percentage of cork and holm oaks in Freixo do Meio are 30 % and

70 %, respectively over a surface of 480 hectares with an average tree density of 70 per hectare. As in Laporta et al. (2021), no (previous) land use change is assumed with the system boundaries. The carbon gains considered were the mean annual increments of holm and cork oaks from the Portuguese National Inventory Reports (Costa Pereira et al., 2022), based on the mean annual increment of oaks, the biomass expansion factor, the root-to-shoot factor, and the carbon fraction. The carbon losses considered were those due to natural mortality of forest stands and from extraction (harvesting or pruning). Balancing the above-ground carbon sequestration with a 30 % presence of cork oaks and 70 % of holm oaks results in a net aboveground carbon sequestration of 1.2 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ when maintaining the traditional montado system in Freixo do Meio.

Due to the nature of the farm characterised by multiple outputs from diverse enterprises, three modelling approaches regarding land occupation and carbon sequestration were taken when assessing the environmental burdens associated with the acorn food value chain:

1. *Integral*: the total surface area of the montado covered by oak trees (480 ha) as well as its associated carbon sequestration (over the 480 ha) were allocated to the acorn food enterprise based on its relative economic revenue to the total revenue of Freixo do Meio's multi-output system (animal, tourism, cork, acorn as food enterprises).

2. *Intermediate*: the actual surface area on which acorns were harvested (50 ha), but in a suboptimal way (a few acorns were collected on that surface area, leaving food for the animals), as well as its associated carbon sequestration (over the 50 ha) were allocated to the acorn as food enterprise based on its relative economic revenue to the total revenue of Freixo do Meio's multi-output system (animal, tourism, cork, acorn as food enterprises).

3. *Focused*: a hypothetical scenario where more focused harvesting of all acorns produced would take place. The surface area necessary to produce the exact quantities of acorns used for human food was calculated, assuming that the oak trees would only be used for the acorn for food enterprise. This scenario therefore attributes the total land occupation (and associated carbon sequestration) for focused acorn food production to the acorn enterprise value chain.

Intermediate and *Integral* approaches represent different system delineation/allocation, with the former attempting to biophysically separate as far as possible the acorn enterprise from the other farm enterprises. Meanwhile, *Focused* is a counterfactual "what if?" the acorns were produced from a dedicated system. This provides insight into what acorn product footprints would look like in a more specialist, less integrated, system. The results from these different approaches will indicate how sensitive LCA results are to both methodological choices, and

Fig. 2. Modelled carbon sequestration and land occupation area for the three scenarios considered. A. Integral scenario; B. Intermediate scenario; C. Focused scenario.

system design, and provide a deeper understanding of how to deal with such multi-output systems.

Therefore, the aboveground carbon sequestration values described above were allocated to the various enterprises at Freixo do Meio depending on their respective percentage contribution to the economic gross revenue of Freixo do Meio. Gross revenue percentages for the acorn food enterprise are recorded in Table S3 (Supplementary Information). A 10.6 % allocation factor for acorn food was distributed among the specific acorn products based on their relative revenues, and values were recorded in **Table S4, Supplementary Information**.

The land occupation of the montado attributed to each acorn product was determined following Eq. (1) and is graphically represented in Fig. 2.

$$Land_{Product,Scenario} = \left(\frac{(Surface_{Scenario} \cdot AF_{Acorn,Enterprise}) \cdot AF_{Product}}{Product_{Sold}} \right) \quad (1)$$

Where:

$Land_{Product,Scenario}$ = land occupation for the production of 1 kg acorn product (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) in a specific scenario (*Integral*, *Intermediate*, or *Focused*) (ha)

$Surface_{Scenario}$ = total surface area modelled for acorn harvesting in a specific scenario (*Integral*, *Intermediate*, or *Focused*) (ha)

$AF_{Acorn,Enterprise}$ = Allocation factor of the acorn food enterprise

$AF_{Product}$ = Economic allocation factor of the acorn product type (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) for the acorn enterprise

$Product_{Sold}$ = Amount of products sold of a same type (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) (kg)

Carbon sequestration associated with the harvest of acorns for human food consumption was calculated based on Eq. (2). Above- and below-ground carbon sequestration in Freixo do Meio are multiplied by the surface area of the montado attributed to the production of 1 kg of acorn product in a specific scenario.

$$Cseq_{Product,Scenario} = (Cseq_{AG} + Cseq_{BG}) \cdot Land_{Product,Scenario} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$Cseq_{Product,Scenario}$ = carbon sequestration attributed to 1 kg of acorn product (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) in a specific scenario (*Integral*, *Intermediate*, or *Focused*) (t CO₂e per kg acorn product)

$Cseq_{AG}$ = aboveground carbon sequestration in Freixo do Meio (t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹)

$Cseq_{BG}$ = belowground carbon sequestration in Freixo do Meio (t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹).

$Land_{Product,Scenario}$ = land occupation attributed to the production of 1 kg of acorn product (fermented acorns, burger patty, pâté, or flour) in a specific scenario (*Integral*, *Intermediate*, or *Focused*) (ha)

2.10. Nitrogen input from animal manure

As the acorn enterprise benefits from the fertilisation of the oak trees from manure produced by the animals, the system boundaries partly included emissions arising from organic N inputs. The N excretion rates of each farm animal in Freixo do Meio were determined based on the Tier 1 approach (Eq. (10.30)) defined in the refined IPCC guidelines (GitarSKIY, 2019). Amounts of N from urine and dung per hectare were recorded in Table 2. The average weight of each animal type was extracted from the Domestic Animal Diversity Information System (FAO, 2024). For simplicity, it was assumed that there was an equal number of male and female animals in each herd. Direct and indirect N₂O emissions from atmospheric deposition of N volatilised and from leaching/runoff from managed soils were calculating following the Tier 1 approach (Eqs. (11.1), (11.9), and (11.10), respectively) from the refined IPCC guidelines (GitarSKIY, 2019). Ammonia emissions to the air from the volatilization of manure and nitrate losses to water (leaching) were also calculated following the refined IPCC guidelines (GitarSKIY, 2019). Following the same approach as for the allocation of carbon

Table 2

N inputs from manure excretion per animal type.

Animal type	Animal number	N excretion (kg N animal ⁻¹ yr ⁻¹)	N excretion (kg N· yr ⁻¹)	N excretion (kg N ha ⁻¹ · yr ⁻¹)
Barrosã cattle	160	96	15,330	32
Alentejo pigs	450	39	17,616	37
Merino sheep	250	9	2217	5
Total				73

sequestration, part of these emissions was then allocated to the acorn as food enterprise based on the quantity of manure deposited on the corresponding land occupation. Grazing intensity and manure deposition on a given area were the same across all modelled scenarios. The varying factor in the model was the acorn harvesting area (which is either the entire, or a portion of, the grazing area) and its associated manure deposition. As manure deposition affects various enterprises (e.g. acorn for human food, cork, other plantations, and animal enterprises), a portion of N deposition impacts was attributed to the acorn for human food enterprise, using the same economic allocation factor as for the carbon sequestration and land occupation.

2.11. Uncertainty modelling

To identify results that are statistically significant, the following approach was used. A modified Null Hypothesis Significance Test (mNHST) using 1000 Monte Carlo runs for each system was run (Mendoza Beltran et al., 2018), testing the following hypothesis: “the production systems delivering two product alternatives (e.g. fermented acorns vs fermented olives/ acorn flour vs wheat flour, etc.) are associated with different environmental impacts” was tested statistically. False positives were excluded using a Bonferroni correction, which is a conservative approach and thus is defensible scientifically, $\alpha_b = 0.005/64 = 0.0005$. The 64 factor stands for the sixteen environmental impact categories, the three modelling options for the acorn product and the conventional alternative. Threshold values were tested with an effect size (d_0) of 0.2, which is a conventional value for NHSTs (Mendoza Beltran et al., 2018).

Several studies of montado systems undertook different approaches to account for below- and/or above-ground carbon sequestration (Table S1, Supplementary Information). The below-ground carbon sequestration of 2.97 ± 1.13 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ presented by Reyes-Palomo et al. (2023) was used in this study, with a triangle distribution with a mode of 2.97 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹, a minimum of 1.84 t CO₂ ha⁻¹.year⁻¹, and a maximum of 4.1 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ (percentage variability of 38.05 %) were used to run the monte carlo analyses. Uncertainty regarding above-ground carbon storage was modelled in the monte carlo analysis using a triangle distribution with a mode of 1.2 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ and a variability of ± 38.05 % (minimum 0.7 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹ and maximum of 1.7 t CO₂ eq. ha⁻¹.year⁻¹), to keep the same percentage variability calculated for the below-ground carbon sequestration in Reyes-Palomo et al. (2023). Besides the carbon sequestration flows, other environmental flows assigned to processes in OpenLCA were given a logarithmic normal uncertainty distribution, with a geometric standard deviation calculated using the Ecoinvent data quality system matrix (Wernet, 2016).

3. Results

The environmental burdens for 1 kg of acorn product and its market alternative across the sixteen environmental impact categories and three land use and carbon sequestration scenarios (*Focused*, *Intermediate* and *Integral*) are recorded in Table 3. The subsections below interpret results for each of the products assessed. The different land and carbon

Table 3
Life cycle impact assessment results for the acorn products assessed and their conventional alternatives.

Impact categories	Unit	Flour				Burger patty					Pate				Pickles			
		Acorn flour			Organic wheat flour	Acorn burger			Soy burger	Beef burger	Acorn pate			Pork/chicken terrine	Fermented acorns			Olives
		Focused	Intermediate	Integral		Focused	Intermediate	Integral			Focused	Intermediate	Integral		Focused	Intermediate	Integral	
Acidification	mol H ⁺ eq	0.01	0.01	0.03	0.03	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.01	0.45	0.02	0.02	0.02	0.09	0.01	0.008	0.025	0.01
Climate change	kg CO ₂ eq	-19.2	-8.4	-88.1	0.5	-4.05	-1.5	-20.1	0.9	38.7	-3.18	-1	-17.1	5.7	-14.7	-6.4	-67.6	-19.2
Ecotoxicity, freshwater	CTUe	32.8	26.6	72.3	8.2	32.4	30.9	41.6	45.7	333.2	82	80.7	90	176.6	26.5	21.7	56.8	32.8
Eutrophication, freshwater	kg P eq	1.60E-04	1.60E-04	1.60E-04	2.00E-04	2.50E-04	2.50E-04	2.50E-04	3.40E-04	1.90E-03	4.10E-04	4.10E-04	4.10E-04	1.00E-03	1.30E-04	1.30E-04	1.30E-04	1.60E-04
Eutrophication, marine	kg N eq	0.11	0.05	0.46	0.02	0.03	0.02	0.11	0.01	0.1	0.03	0.02	0.1	0.02	0.081	0.038	0.351	0.11
Eutrophication, terrestrial	mol N eq	0.22	0.12	0.87	0.12	0.07	0.05	0.22	0.03	1.99	0.11	0.09	0.24	0.4	0.17	0.09	0.67	0.22
Human toxicity, cancer	CTUh	7.50E-10	7.50E-10	7.50E-10	2.00E-09	7.40E-10	7.40E-10	7.40E-10	1.60E-09	1.50E-08	3.00E-09	3.00E-09	3.00E-09	4.80E-09	6.00E-10	6.00E-10	6.00E-10	7.50E-10
Human toxicity, non-cancer	CTUh	3.40E-08	3.40E-08	3.50E-08	2.20E-07	3.60E-08	3.60E-08	3.60E-08	3.00E-08	6.40E-07	2.50E-07	2.50E-07	2.50E-07	1.10E-07	2.80E-08	2.70E-08	2.80E-08	3.40E-08
Ionising radiation	kBq U-235 eq	0.04	0.04	0.04	0.01	0.05	0.05	0.05	1.25	1.51	0.08	0.08	0.08	1.58	0.034	0.034	0.034	0.04
Land use	Point	992	473	4290	9	326	205	1095	107	2295	411	306	1079	301	762	363	3294	992
Ozone depletion	kg CFC11 eq	1.30E-08	1.30E-08	1.30E-08	3.60E-09	1.20E-08	1.20E-08	1.20E-08	8.40E-08	7.20E-07	2.10E-08	2.10E-08	2.10E-08	4.50E-07	1.00E-08	1.00E-08	1.00E-08	1.30E-08
Particulate matter	kg disease inc.	2.20E-06	1.10E-06	9.40E-06	1.80E-07	5.60E-07	2.90E-07	2.20E-06	5.40E-08	3.00E-06	5.60E-07	3.30E-07	2.00E-06	6.70E-07	1.70E-06	8.50E-07	7.20E-06	2.20E-06
Photochemical ozone formation	kg NMVOC eq	0.009	0.009	0.009	0.003	0.004	0.004	0.004	0.003	0.047	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.013	0.007	0.007	0.007	0.009
Resource use, fossils	MJ	11.2	11.2	11.2	3.4	7.9	7.9	7.9	32.2	84.7	13.6	13.6	13.6	60	8.866	8.866	8.866	11.2
Resource use, minerals and metals	kg Sb eq	5.20E-06	5.20E-06	5.20E-06	1.80E-06	3.60E-06	3.60E-06	3.60E-06	4.40E-06	5.70E-05	5.90E-06	5.90E-06	5.90E-06	2.10E-05	4.80E-06	4.80E-06	4.80E-06	5.20E-06
Water use	m ³ depriv.	0.2	0.2	0.2	3.1	1.6	1.6	1.6	0.4	6.9	5.8	5.8	5.8	4.9	0.2	0.2	0.2	0.2

sequestration allocation approaches influenced the acidification, climate change, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine and terrestrial eutrophication, land use, and particulate matter impact categories. While the *Integral* approach was allocated the largest carbon sequestration amount per kg end product, it had the largest burdens attributed across the above-mentioned impact categories. The hypothetical *Focused* approach was associated with environmental burdens that were larger than those of *Intermediate* but smaller than those of *Integral*. The *Intermediate* approach was associated with the smallest carbon sequestration and environmental burden attribution.

Comparative environmental efficiency between the acorn-based products and the conventional market alternatives varied depending on the impact category and the product type. The acorn-based foods that were benchmarked against a meat product displayed lower environmental burdens across 12 to 13 (burger patty) and 10 to 12 (pâté) out of the 16 impact categories assessed, compared with the reference conventional product. Acorn-based foods that were benchmarked against a plant-based alternative were associated with lower environmental burdens across 2 to 3 impact categories out of the 16 studied, and with higher environmental burdens across 10 to 12 impact categories out of 16. The large difference between the plant-based alternatives and the acorn-based products can mainly be explained with the over 10-fold higher olive/wheat yields per hectare compared with acorn yields. Moreover just 56 % of harvested acorns end up in the acorn foods – the remainder is returned to the soil or fed to animals, due to insufficient quality. Area-related manure emissions are then consequently attributed to small quantities of acorn foods. Conversely, the large land areas attributed to the acorn products resulted in large carbon sequestration values, and therefore lower (negative) climate change burdens (Table 3). General environmental results for 1 kg of acorn products and market alternatives. Green cells indicate that the environmental burden of the acorn product was statistically significantly lower than the conventional alternative, while cells in red indicate a statistically significantly higher burden. Cells in white show no statistical significance. For the burger patty comparison, the acorn burger patty is compared to the beef burger patty.

3.1. Burger patties

All acorn burger patty models were associated with lower

environmental burdens than the beef burger patty across most impact categories (Table 3). The beef burger patty was associated with significantly lower burdens across the human toxicity non-cancer category, and no significant difference was found across the human toxicity cancer category for all acorn burger patties and between the *Integral* approach and beef burger patty. All other burdens across all categories were significantly smaller for the acorn-based patties, with 89–97 % smaller terrestrial eutrophication, 52–91 % smaller land occupation, 97–98 % smaller acidification, etc. (Table 3).

Results across the six categories with the highest normalised environmental burdens and the climate change category for the acorn based burger patty and alternatives were recorded in Fig. 3, excluding the toxicity-related impact categories due to high uncertainty in these impacts (European Commission, 2018). For the acorn burger patty, marine eutrophication was the category with the highest normalised scores across the three scenarios, followed by particulate matter, terrestrial eutrophication and land use, and acidification. A different pattern was observed with the beef patty, with the highest normalised score being terrestrial eutrophication, followed by acidification, marine eutrophication, particulate matter, climate change, and lastly land use. The soy-based patty was associated with a higher normalised marine eutrophication burden, followed by terrestrial eutrophication, acidification, land use, climate change, and lastly particulate matter.

Process contributions for the acorn burger patty across the same impact categories presented in Fig. 3 were recorded in Fig. 4. Manure deposition was responsible for most of the burdens across climate change, terrestrial and marine eutrophication, and particulate matter (on the basis that the manure provides nutrient inputs to the acorn production). Climate change burdens associated with manure deposition were however compensated by the carbon sequestration achieved. The burdens associated with the processing phase were comparatively minor.

The additional ingredients in the burger patty contributed 32 %–54 % and 7 %–36 % to the acidification and terrestrial eutrophication burdens, respectively. These mainly came from the chickpea production that released ammonia to the air.

3.2. Pickles (fermented acorns and olives)

All three approaches modelled for fermented acorns were associated

Fig. 3. Normalised results per kg of burger patty across the six categories with the highest environmental burdens and climate change.

Fig. 4. Process contributions per kg of acorn burger patties across the five categories with the highest environmental burdens and climate change.

with environmental burdens that were statistically significantly larger than fermented olives across all assessed impact categories, except for climate change and ozone depletion, for which the fermented acorns were associated with a significantly lower burdens, and for freshwater ecotoxicity and water use, across which no statistical difference was found (Table 3). While 1 kg of fermented acorns was associated with a carbon saving of -6.4 to -67.6 kg CO₂ eq., it was also associated with a 7 to 74 times higher land occupation and 28 to 267 times higher marine eutrophication burden than olives (Table 3).

Process contributions of the fermented acorns are recorded in Fig. S1 (Supplementary Information). As for the acorn burger patty, manure deposition was associated with the largest share of burdens across climate change, terrestrial and marine eutrophication, and particulate matter mainly due to the resulting emissions of nitrate to water for marine eutrophication and ammonia to the air for the other impact categories. Climate change burdens associated with manure deposition were however compensated by the carbon sequestration achieved. The burdens associated with the processing phase were comparatively minor, with a 4 % to 13 % contribution to the total acidification and marine eutrophication burdens, 1 to 11 % contribution to total particulate matter, and 4 % or less contribution to the total terrestrial eutrophication and land use burdens. Process contributions of the fermented acorns were recorded in Fig. S2 (Supplementary Information).

3.3. Pâtés

The acorn pâté was associated with significantly lower environmental burdens across 10 to 12 impact categories compared with the terrine (Table 3). Environmental trade-offs present across all modelling approaches for the acorn pâté were identified across water use (17 % larger) and human toxicity non-cancer (1.3 times larger). Trade-offs that applied to the *Focused* and *Integral* approaches were found across the land use, marine eutrophication, and particulate matter categories.

Process contributions of the acorn pâté are recorded in Fig. S2 (Supplementary Information). While manure was still associated with a large share of the burdens across the marine (51 % to 91 % of total) and terrestrial eutrophication (17 % to 66 % of total) and particulate matter (55 % to 92 % of total) categories, other ingredients in the acorn pâté also contributed substantially towards acidification (66 % to 79 % of total), land use (51 % to 91 % of total), and terrestrial eutrophication (17 % to 64 % of total) burdens. The high contribution to acidification and terrestrial burdens was due to olive oil and bell pepper production, releasing ammonia to the air.

3.4. Flour

Acorn flour was associated with significantly lower climate change and freshwater eutrophication burdens than the organic wheat flour, but also with significantly higher burdens across all other categories assessed except for human toxicity categories and water use, where no statistical significance was found. The *Focus* and *Intermediate* approaches were also associated with a 61 % and 70 % lower acidification burden than the organic wheat flour (Table 3).

Process contributions of the acorn flour are recorded in Fig. S3 (Supplementary Information). The percentage gross revenues for the acorn as food enterprise consists of the sum of the percentage gross revenues achieved through acorns sold at Freixo do Meio and the percentage gross revenues achieved through acorns sold at the canteen of Freixo do Meio. As the flour is made solely with acorns, the deposited manure is responsible for most of the burdens. It was associated with 27 % to 78 %, 97 % to 99 %, 77 % to 97 %, and 86 % to 98 % of total acidification, marine eutrophication, terrestrial eutrophication, and particulate matter, respectively. This was again mainly due to the resulting emissions of nitrate to water for marine eutrophication and ammonia to the air for the other impact categories.

4. Discussion

This is the first study to our knowledge that assesses the environmental impact of acorns as ingredients for direct human consumption. The study attempts to deal with a complex multifunctional system supporting numerous activities and outputs, by first dividing these activities into “enterprises” (biophysical separation) as far as possible and then allocating burdens of activities that cross over several enterprises. Indeed, strictly speaking, tree growth and its associated carbon sequestration would be attributed entirely to trees and their activities, while livestock are not required for this phenomenon to take place. Our results show that acorn-based food products were associated with a statistically significantly lower climate change burden than their conventional alternatives. The acorn-based foods were associated with a carbon saving (negative carbon footprint) due to the allocated carbon sequestration exceeding the climate change emissions caused by the processing of the acorns. These results suggest that using acorns as plant-based ingredients for direct human consumption could be part of a more sustainable and diverse diet (Willett et al., 2019), supporting landscapes with greater carbon storage. Expanding the use of acorns for direct human consumption could eventually lead to less acorns available as pig feed, although as seen in this case study nearly 50 % of the harvested acorns are left for animal feed, in addition to the acorns left on the ground when harvesting takes place.

LCAs are typically more focused at an enterprise level, whereas agroforestry farms have numerous units, and this study aimed to make this distinction. The *Integral* scenario can be interpreted a reflection of the current system, as it reflects a limited demand for acorns for human food. If the demand for acorns increases (due to policy incentives, consumer demand, etc.), the system representation will shift towards one that is closer to the *Intermediate* approach. Finally, a more intensive approach would be reached with a further increased use of acorns for human food, and this is represented by the *Focused* approach. Nevertheless, the aggregate picture of the farm does not change, but how each resource and impact are allocated to the acorn foods are. Following the results of the different approaches, maintaining the plurality of outputs in the *montado* system but increasing the harvest of acorns for direct human food while still respecting their use in other enterprises would yield a lower environmental impact per kg of acorn product and would be a path to consider.

However, including manure emissions in the *Focused* approach presents pitfalls. On one hand, biophysical separation is difficult because it is assumed that animal manure nutrient cycling (fertilisation) is integral to the system. Nonetheless, this approach may over-attribute manure emissions to acorns, as it assumes no manure emissions belong to livestock products. Following the different results, it appears that the *Intermediate* approach is associated with the lowest environmental burdens across all impact categories except for climate change, across which the *Integral* approach has the largest saving. It can be interpreted that the high eutrophication burdens in the *Integral* approach are due to the current acorn amount harvested being lower than what could be harvested over the same surface area, which would spread the burdens over more acorn foods.

It is not possible to compare the results on acorn production of this study with any LCA studies, since existing studies of *montado* systems do not look at acorn as a functional unit. Existing LCA studies of *montado* systems with an animal product functional unit did not attribute any environmental burden to acorn production and oak tree management (Horrillo et al., 2020; Lamnatou et al., 2022; Reyes-Palomo et al., 2022, 2023), only accounting for purchased feed emissions and not “natural” feed (grass and acorns). Therefore, one of the novelties of this study is the attribution of an environmental impact to acorn production. The only LCA study of a *montado* system with an animal product functional unit that modelled a difference in emissions from the use of acorn was García-Gudiño et al. (2020), who quantified the average intake of acorn per pig, so as to calculate more accurate nutrient excretion on farm.

However, here again no environmental burden was attributed to the acorns.

Studies that did consider oak tree management (stand establishment, stand tending, cork stripping, field recovery) in their life cycle inventory are those of cork production (Dias et al., 2014; González-García et al., 2013). Dias et al. (2014) assessed montado systems with a planting density of 400 oak trees per hectare in Portugal and up to 700 oak trees per hectare with 400 cork productive trees and 300 growing trees in Spain. Tree density was much lower in González-García et al. (2013), with only 50 to 100 trees per hectare, much more in line with the Freixo do Meio farm assessed here. However, these LCA studies did not include any animals, and therefore fertiliser addition and other tree management practices have to be done by humans. The environmental burdens calculated in these two studies can therefore not be used for any comparison with the results of this study.

The unusually high carbon savings associated with the acorn-based foods may be surprising at first impression. However, these numbers represent extensive montado systems where carbon sequestration over a large land area is attributed to a small quantity of product. The findings of this study are in line with Dias et al. (2014)'s discussion point that they would also expect a negative biogenic CO₂ balance with a 100 year time horizon, as cork oak trees continue to sequester CO₂ during their 170–200 year lifespan. Minimal processing burdens of the acorns, as in this study, could then result in an overall negative climate change footprint if a big enough proportion of the carbon sequestration taking place is allocated to the acorn products. However, such an approach also results in large land occupation burdens, as yields are low when compared to conventionally grown crops. This flags the modest scalability potential of such production systems in the overall food system.

Across most of the other fifteen impact categories assessed, and where acorn-based foods were compared to meat products (i.e. the acorn-based burger patty and the acorn pâté), the environmental burdens of the former were markedly smaller. This is not surprising as meat products, especially beef-based, are associated with larger environmental impacts than plant-based ones (Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Willett et al., 2019). However, there were some notable exceptions, including a significantly higher water use burden for the acorn pâté than the meat terrine.

A manure deposition of 73 N ha⁻¹·yr⁻¹ was calculated in this study based on animal numbers and types, which exceeds by more than four times the critical load range of 15 to 17.5 kg N·ha⁻¹·yr⁻¹ for the sclerophyllous Mediterranean forests (Aguillaume et al., 2017). Therefore, reducing this input through the reduction in stocking rates would reduce these environmental burdens. Although manure deposition is linked directly with pig (meat) production, it also contributes an important nutrient cycling function in the montado system and therefore is considered in scope of the acorn food system.

The marked differences in environmental burdens between the different land and carbon sequestration allocation approaches across the acidification, climate change, freshwater ecotoxicity, marine and terrestrial eutrophication, land use, and particulate matter impact categories highlight the need for testing sensitivity of results to these different approaches if these categories are assessed. Selecting one approach over another comes with advantages and trade-offs in terms of environmental sustainability, with *Integral* having higher carbon savings but higher burdens across the other categories. *Focused* and *Intermediate* result in lower carbon savings, but also lower environmental burdens across the remaining categories.

Numerous assumptions were made in this study. Acorn yields were taken from the literature as no primary data were available. Nevertheless, this uncertainty was addressed with the triangle distribution with a + or –50 % yield difference in the Monte Carlo analyses. The use of proxies for some minor ingredients of the acorn foods was required due to missing processes in the LCA databases: onion for garlic, bell pepper for pepper paste, and industrial boiling for cooking. Again here, uncertainty was addressed here with the Monte Carlo analyses, but ideally

more research should be performed to fill in these data gaps. This research could also include the missing herbs used in the recipes, which are present in minor quantities. Another limitation is that emissions from end-of-life composting of shells are ignored.

An extensive analysis around different system configurations, as well as an attempt to separate as much as possible the acorn as food sub-system from other farm sub-systems to minimise allocation were performed. Nevertheless, it was not possible to remove entirely the need for allocation in the model, and therefore economic allocation was applied. While economic allocation can be volatile and may not reflect biophysical realities, this approach was still adopted in this study, as the other co-products of the system have a very different function and physical properties of all co-products do not share similar values. Moreover, adopting an economic allocation approach aligns with decision-making based on financial relevance. As discussed earlier, economics are a key aspect in montado systems due to the importance of maintaining these traditional systems despite economic challenges. A mass-based or biophysical allocation was not performed because the system has as outputs a mix of services and products combined (e.g. restaurant, hotel, and acorns), and output data of other enterprises were not provided.

It was assumed that the products that are being compared to the acorn products are representative enough of the conventional alternatives that the acorn foods could substitute. These products were selected as they were readily available from the LCA database Agribalyse (Colomb et al., 2015). It must be kept in mind that footprints found in other studies are not directly comparable, due to different system boundaries, methods, etc. However, for superficial comparison purposes, a search in the literature was performed and revealed similar footprints for the conventional products. Brito and Fernandes-Silva (2022) calculated a footprint of around 0.25 kg CO₂e per kg olives at farm gate (without the fermentation stage), which is higher than the 0.03 kg CO₂e per kg fermented olive used here (without carbon sequestration). Apart from the different methods package, numerous parameters can explain this difference, such as yields from Brito and Fernandes-Silva (2022) being of 3209 kg·ha⁻¹ against Ecoinvent's yield of 5000 kg·ha⁻¹ (Wernet, 2016). Other LCA studies of olive production found burdens that ranged between 0.095 and 0.5 kg CO₂e per ton of olive (Romero-Gómez et al., 2017; Salomone et al., 2015), which is still above the value used in this study. Thus, fermented acorns could be associated with a climate change burden that is equivalent or lower than that of fermented olives, contrary to the results of this study. The same carbon sequestration as the hypothetical *Focused* approach was assigned based on land occupied for olive production. Carbon sequestration happening in the *Focused* approach was chosen as it was assumed that the olives were grown as stand-alone crops in olive groves. The olive trees were allocated the same aboveground carbon sequestration amount per hectare as in the hypothetical *Focused* approach. However, olive trees are smaller than oak trees, resulting in a relatively smaller carbon sequestration than for the oak trees. Even with such a conservative approach that increased the carbon savings of fermented olives, the fermented acorns were associated with significantly higher carbon savings than fermented olives, confirming that the acorn product performs better in the climate change category.

Regarding wheat flour, a footprint of 0.86 kg CO₂e per kg or organic flour was found in the literature (Chiriacò et al., 2017), which is higher than the footprint used in this study. Comparative environmental efficiency of acorn flour would therefore increase if this value was used. Numerous studies on the environmental impact of beef burger patties and soybean burger patties, such as Keoleian and Heller (2018), Saget et al. (2021) who associated between 33 kg and 55 kg CO₂e per kg of raw beef patty, and between 4 kg and 10 kg CO₂e per kg of raw soybean-based burger patty. The values used in this study for both burger patty types are comparatively lower. The only study on meat pâté that was found for comparison was by Teixeira et al. (2013), who found a footprint varying between around 2 kg and 3 kg CO₂e per kg of pork

pâté without packaging, depending on the product assessed. These values are lower than the 5.7 kg CO₂e per kg of pork and chicken terrine used in this study, but still higher than the climate change burden of the acorn pâté.

The environmental footprint of the acorn-based products was calculated based on the current technologies used within the farm. However, several opportunities for optimising various steps along the production chain could potentially reduce the environmental burdens associated with these products. For example, challenges in the harvesting stage include the fact that acorns are picked by hand, which is time consuming and expensive, and for which we did not attribute an environmental burden. While on-site processing may present advantages due to reduced transportation burdens, small-scale processing is generally less efficient than industrial processing due to smaller, non-optimized equipment. This is well illustrated here, with the smokehouse to dry the acorns being a slow and expensive process. In 2023, a large drier was purchased but has yet to be used. Other approaches should be investigated, such as the shelling of acorns before drying, better sorting of spoilt acorns before drying, the use of solar greenhouses, and the use of a dehumidifier. The current system is far from optimised with respect to acorns for human consumption, though that may be because it supports many other outputs – and there may be a trade-off between singular output optimisation and maintaining multifunctionality.

The study by von Essen et al. (2019) presented a scenario where cork oak tree density was increased from 80 trees·ha⁻¹ to 120 trees·ha⁻¹, resulting in a 13.5 % increase in carbon sequestration compared to the farm's current carbon sequestration amounts. Increasing oak tree density in Freixo do Meio may provide the same benefits and additional carbon could be sequestered as in the above-mentioned studies. However, as highlighted by von Essen et al. (2019), currently such an action would provide a negligible economic reward as there is no viable carbon sequestration payment system. The reality is that there has been a tendency over the last 25 years to transform these traditional agroforestry systems into grasslands or shrublands in Portugal, and it was shown that both an abandonment and a grazing intensification of such systems resulted in an increase in emissions of 1.2 and 1.3 tons CO₂e·ha⁻¹·year⁻¹, respectively (Laporta et al., 2021). Freixo do Meio provides an example on how to diversify economic activities on a traditional montado system and therefore how to maintain such landscapes as part of a self-sustaining economic model. Moreover, besides carbon sequestration, it is important to note that traditional management of montado systems is associated with other benefits that are not adequately captured by performing an LCA. These include the provision of ecosystem services, such as enhancement of biodiversity, prevention of wildfires, erosion control, enhanced nutrient cycling, income diversification, preservation of a cultural heritage, etc. (Guimaraes et al., 2023; von Essen et al., 2019). Such food products fit with the EU Green Deal and Farm to Fork Strategy, which aim to promote sustainable food value chains and valorise underutilized crops. However, while the provision of ecosystem services is key for preserving environmental/human health and well-being, those that do not contribute to farmer revenues are increasingly at risk, due to globalisation and public policy incentives that favour specialisation and system simplification that are diametrically opposed to complex silvo-pastoral systems like montado systems. Specifically, over-stocking and reduction of tree density in montado systems are major common risks that montado systems are facing (Guimaraes et al., 2023). Using acorns for making human food products, as shown in this study, instead of animal feed, could counter these risks without any policy intervention.

A significant challenge that montado systems face and that affects yearly stability of acorn-based food production is climate change, which acts as a direct stressor and a catalyst for other threats (Bratu et al., 2025). Higher temperatures and lower precipitations weaken oak trees and damage their physiological functions, making them more vulnerable to pathogens, including to *Phytophthora cinnamomi*, a microscopic

fungi that causes root diseases (Haavik et al., 2015). Warmer temperatures in autumn increase dormancy of early-fallen acorns, delaying their shoot growth and therefore leading to less established seedlings when summer droughts arise (Leiva and Perelló-Rodríguez, 2024). Garcia-Barreda et al. (2023) performed a 19-year study on 150 holm oaks in Spain, assessing the effect of drought on some oak tree parameters. They identified both an immediate effect, with an acorn production close to zero during the drought year, and a longer-term effect, where the oak trees compensated by producing significantly more acorns than predicted in the year following a drought year. However, this study could not investigate how oak trees would react with a higher drought frequency. Importantly, not all oak trees are equally affected by climate change, with holm oaks showing higher resilience than cork oaks (Bratu et al., 2025). Some studies investigated a number of measures to help cork oaks cope with climate change. Domingo et al. (2020) found that holm oaks with 50 % of stools in their basal area thinned showed greater drought resistance than other holm oaks, and all holm oaks showed drought resilience with leaf recovery the year following the drought. Nurse plants, such as shrubs or other trees, improve resilience to drought as they improve soil conditions and provide shade to seedlings (Garcia-Fayos et al., 2020). However, these nurse plants are also threatened by increasing aridity, leading to an overall decrease in stand regeneration. Recognising these threats, expansion of montado systems could shift to other regions as climate change progresses (e.g. further north).

Assuming there is a large proportion of *Quercus rotundifolia*, there would be space for scaling up the production of such acorn foods, since montado systems cover together >4 million hectares in Spain and Portugal. This would provide an additional revenue stream from the land, diversifying activities and therefore building up resilience for the farmers. In the case of Freixo do Meio, as mentioned previously, far from all acorns are exploited, and there is therefore potential for increasing production of the acorn foods on this land. Such a development, however, should not exceed a certain threshold, so that the other uses of oak trees (e.g. animal feed and tourism) are not negatively affected. Further research needs to be done to determine this threshold. Taking an average yield of to 387 kg of acorns produced per hectare per year, this represents >1.55 billion kg of acorns produced. These acorns could potentially be processed into 695 thousand tonnes of acorn flour, or 2.3 million tonnes of acorn burger patties, with a resulting climate change saving of 14 million tonnes CO₂e per year, or 130 million tonnes CO₂e per year, if substituting the wheat flour or beef burger patties assessed in this study, respectively, using the results of the *Focused* scenario, as it represents a more intensive acorn for human food production system.

Subsidising agroforestry systems with oak trees, classifying oak cultivation for food under eco-schemes or greening measures, and funding the regeneration of montado systems that have oak trees that produce human-edible acorns are policies that could support the transition of montado systems towards a system like Freixo do Meio's. Additionally, providing funding for improving selection and processing techniques of acorns for human food could incentivise other montado farms to adopt such a use for their acorns. From a regulatory perspective, developing a clear label for acorn-based products could increase consumer awareness and acceptability of these products, such as gluten-free, low glycaemic index, rich in fibre.

5. Conclusions

This study provides the first environmental footprints of acorns, providing burdens of processed acorn foods for direct human consumption, ranging from traditional (flours and fermented acorns) to more complex products (burger patties, pâtés). Acorns collected from the case study farm come from a complex multi-output system that presents challenges when calculating footprints of individual foods. Selected approaches to allocate land use (including animal fertilisation) and carbon sequestration effects to acorn foods indicate that these foods

are associated with significantly lower climate change burdens than their counterpart conventional food products. Most of the acorn foods are associated with a net carbon saving (i.e. negative carbon footprint), of up to -88.1 kg CO₂ eq. for a kg of acorn flour with the *Integral* approach, when accounting for above- and below-ground carbon sequestration. The acorn foods that replace meat are also associated with significantly lower burdens across most of the 15 other impact categories assessed, terrestrial eutrophication, land use, and acidification. Acorn flour and fermented acorns, however, are associated with higher burdens than wheat flour and fermented olives across most of the other impact categories. This is mostly due to the high nitrogen input from animal manure deposition, which exceeds the critical load range for N for this type of ecosystem. However, depending on the conventional product used and the secondary LCA data of these products, results may differ and acorn foods could have a similar or even lower burden. This study therefore supports the fact that diversification of traditional montado systems to provide acorns as direct food for human consumption could help maintain traditional agroforestry systems whilst avoiding large impacts from intensification of conventional food systems. However, effects of climate change, especially higher drought frequencies, pose a threat to such systems (as to other food systems in this climatic zone). Careful management and planning where to establish new montado systems could mitigate these effects.

Ethical statement - studies in humans and animals

The authors declare that this study did not involve human participants or animal experiments. Therefore, ethical approval and informed consent were not required.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Sophie Saget: Writing – original draft, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **David Styles:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Marcela Porto Costa:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Michael Williams:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

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